

**Evaluating Synthetic Tabular Data Generation for Economic Modeling: A
Comparison of CTGAN and Copula Approaches**

Davit Tbileli

*Bachelor's Project Report is submitted for the Economics Program of International School of Economics
at Tbilisi State University*

Project Supervisor: Valida Pantsulaia

Tbilisi, 2025

Contents

- List of Abbreviations 3
- Abstract..... 4
- Introduction 5
- Literature Review 6
- Methodology..... 8
 - Synthetic Data Generation and Evaluation Techniques 9
 - Data Description & Source..... 12
 - Data Preprocessing 13
- Results and Findings..... 14
 - Model using real-world data..... 14
 - Model Using Copula..... 16
 - Model Using CTGAN..... 21
 - 100% synthetic, 20% real-world data in training..... 24
 - 50% synthetic, 50% real-world data 24
- Conclusion..... 27
- Bibliography 29

List of Abbreviations

AUC - area under the curve

CDF – Cumulative Distribution Function

CM - Confusion matrix

CTGAN – Conditional Tabular Generative Adversarial Network

FCA - Financial Conduct Authority

GAN – Generative Adversarial Network

GridSearchCV - Grid Search Cross Validation

ID - Identification

LLM – Large Language Model

LLN – The Law of Large Numbers

NA - Not Applicable

NaN - Not a Number

OvR - One-vs-Rest

RandomizedSearchCV - Randomized Search Cross Validation

ROC - Receiver-operating characteristic curve

SD – Synthetic Data

SDV - synthetic data vault

SMOTE – Synthetic Minority Oversampling Technique

XGBoost - Extreme Gradient Boost

Abstract

This thesis explores the use of synthetic tabular data in economic modeling with the focus on financial analysis. It compares two rather popular methods for generating synthetic data – Conditional Tabular Generative Adversarial Network (CTGAN) and Gaussian Copula. The objective of this comparison is to see how well each of these algorithms mimics the data from the real world and how well the models trained on the synthetic data perform against the benchmark model – trained on the real-world data. This process is useful in determining the potential value of synthetic data in the financial sector – how effective would it be for different institutions to utilize it in order to address the problems such as unavailability of data. The comparison is done by evaluating the performance of fully synthetic and hybrid models and different metrics, such as predictive accuracy, F1 score and ROC AUC score. The model used is the Extreme Gradient Boost (XGBoost). Experimentation takes place with the portions of synthetic and real-world data, including 100% synthetic and 50/50 setups. Results show that the Copula was outperformed by the CTGAN algorithm, achieving better metrics of model and better matching of the data with its synthetic counterpart. However, the final result were disappointing compared to the benchmark, unveiling the limitations of these methods.

Introduction

Modern economic landscape is heavily dependent on the financial sector. Hence, it is of significant importance to accurately weigh the financial risk and make realistic economic forecasts. For these to happen the necessary step is financial analysis/modeling. There are certain challenges that usually arise in the process. Commonly one of the challenges is the scarcity of proper data – it might not be sufficiently granular, widely available or it may be of low quality. Moreover, absence of proper data could be due to a number of additional reasons, such as: privacy and legal concerns, infrastructural issues, high costs, etc. It is becoming increasingly hard to obtain proper data with the traditional methods, hence analysts and policymakers are facing a difficult reality.

An innovative approach is necessary to address the above mentioned challenges. One of the more known methods is synthetic data (SD) generation, more precisely, generation of synthetic tabular data. The idea behind this is to mimic the real-world data enough to keep the statistical significance between the variables. However, data will not be repeated. If the information is considered sensitive, this fact along with the removal of the private identifiers (such as age, ID, name, etc.) ensures that there is no possibility of info leakage. This matter will be discussed in minute detail further on.

Synthetic data generation is not a new concept - one of the earliest¹ and most notable examples was introduced by Rubin (1993) about the generation of synthetic data from the available microdata to increase the volume while keeping the statistical properties intact. At the time, it was not actively adopted because of the certain challenges, including unavailability of proper algorithm for data generation and huge computational costs for the time. However today, both technology and the methods are suitable for this mission. Thanks to the advances in computational methods, including machine learning and Monte Carlo simulations, it is now possible to generate high quality synthetic data that can be used for various tasks, such as hypothesis testing, model validation, development of certain economic insights. This thesis explores the potential of synthetic tabular data in revolutionizing financial analysis while also providing the necessary tools/methods for its generation and evaluation.

The primary objective of this research is to investigate and show the actual benefit of using the synthetic tabular data in financial services. Furthermore, promotion of the mentioned utility could be beneficial on societal level – synthetic data can create equal environment for the market competitors. As an example, let us consider the banking sector – as time goes on, it becomes evident that data science becomes more and more attractive for banks. However, the goliaths have an advantage compared to the smaller banks because of the vast amounts of high quality data, which is often not accessible for the newer or smaller banks. Providing them with synthetic

¹ This paper is not the first in the field, there were several before. This one is the most notable.

data can increase banks' market power and give them an edge. Society would indeed benefit from the fiercer competition and decreased monopoly/oligopoly.

What makes this topic relevant is the fact that, as mentioned previously, the field of synthetic data generation is relatively new. Even though synthetic data is largely used in the image recognition and Large Language Model (LLM), it is still an emerging technique in regards of the financial landscape. There are only a few use cases and none of them have yet left the so called "sandbox" state (the reason being uncertainty due to lack of experimentation, not lack of reliability). The most famous example is a report by Financial Conduct Authority (FCA) of the United Kingdom, creating a sandbox with synthetic data of multiple variables accessible for anyone. This report (Financial Conduct Authority (FCA), 2024) will be further discussed in the thesis.

This thesis is organized as follows: the following chapter discusses the relevant literature regarding the synthetic data generation, mainly theory, upsides and downsides, and use cases. The third chapter is about the methodology – tools used for the SD generation for this thesis, common methods and data (source and manipulations in the preprocessing), the algorithms/techniques used in the model. After that, the model will be created and the chapter will be dedicated for the discussion of the results and key findings, comparing the model generated with synthetic data with its counterpart – model with the real-world data.

The main question of the thesis is **if there is any value in using the synthetic data in the financial sector**. For that following should be considered - how SD compares to its real-world data counterpart as a benchmark and generally what added value can it generate. Last section covered in the thesis – conclusion - will address the main question and summarize the findings of the paper.

Literature Review

Before carrying on with the literature review, it should be noted that despite the fact that the field of synthetic data generation is relatively new, the findings are still very informative. Several papers/reports are to be discussed in this chapter, all giving unique insights on the topic of SD.

Literature review will start by analyzing the findings in one of the most recent reports by the FCA - Using Synthetic Data in Financial Services (Financial Conduct Authority (FCA), 2024). The mentioned report is highly informative and has various useful findings. Firstly, it discusses the benefits of the synthetic data. Among many benefits, data augmentation is considered to be the most significant one, as it enlarges the dataset and helps reduce the bias. It is statistically proven by Bernoulli (1713) that higher quantity of data always leads to statistical accuracy. This is called the Law of Large Numbers (LLN).

It is not unusual to encounter types of trade-offs between three key variables (so called “trinity”²) in the financial and economic fields and apparently SD is not an exception either. This brings us to another key point presented in the report that is the SD trinity – fidelity, privacy and utility. These are the three main consideration to make when generating or evaluating the synthetic data. Fidelity –depicts how accurately the data resembles the real-world data. Privacy shows how safe the SD is and how it masks the data in order to prevent the re-identification. There are many privacy-enhancing techniques and some will be used for SD generation and discussed in the next chapter. Lastly, utility shows how statistically significant is the synthetic data compared to its real world counterpart. The tradeoff arises in a following manner – high fidelity and utility vs privacy. If the data has a very minor loss of statistical significance while perfectly (or close to it) resembling the real-world data, it is highly likely that the privacy will be alarmingly low. Same principle applied if reversed. It is important to have a well balanced approach in order to mitigate the risks of leakage and the problem with statistical insignificance.

Another important topic discussed in the FCA report is the significance of the proportion of real world and synthetic data while constructing the model. For different portions the changes from the benchmark are also different (refer to Figure 1). It is important to find a “golden point” for which the portion will be high enough for the data generation to make sense, while also having non-alarming deviation from the benchmark.

Figure 1. Deviations from the benchmark for the different portions of data

Data source	Description	Accuracy change
Real-life data only	Only real-life data used for training	Benchmark
Synthetic data + real-life data	50% synthetic data, 50% real data used	-2.5% of the benchmark
Synthetic data + real-life data	70% synthetic data, 30% real data used	-5.0% of the benchmark
Synthetic data only	Only synthetic data used for training	-32.0% of the benchmark

Another paper that significantly contributed in forming this thesis is (Lei Xu, 2019) - Modeling Tabular Data using Conditional GAN. The authors of the paper invented and naturally were first to test Conditional Tabular Generative Adversarial Network (CTGAN) against its older counterpart Tabular Generative Adversarial Network (GAN). The detailed explanation of the working

² Good example would be the Mundell-Fleming trilemma – “The Impossible Trinity” (Fleming, 1962). The idea is that there is no possible way of having all three – fixed exchange rate, independent monetary policy and free capital mobility.

principles of these algorithms will be provided in the next chapter. While GAN is doing the job ideally when working with the LLM's and synthesizing images, it struggles with the tabular data. The reason is inability to work with mixed types of data (continuous and categorical) and imbalanced distributions. Additionally there might be occasional mode collapses – focusing on only one feature distribution out of possible few.

While researching the Copula method for SD generation, work by Kamthe (2021) turned out to be a great help. It discussed the advantages of the mentioned method – ability to work with mixed types of data, cost efficiency, etc. The comparison of Copula and CTGAN can be found in the next chapter with detailed analysis of each method. In the process of listing the pros and cons, the following papers were used - (Lei Xu, 2019), (Li, Zhao, & Fu, 2020), (Sanket Kamthe, 2021).

It should be mentioned that the field of synthetic data generation, especially in the case of financial services, is still emerging. As a result, there is very limited literature that can be reviewed which naturally makes this section relatively brief. Nonetheless, the available sources gave very deep and insightful aspects about generation techniques, SD quality valuation and many more topics.

Methodology

This chapter will discuss the synthetic data generation methods, followed by a detailed provision of data that is to be used in this research (including origins, preprocessing, and validation). But beforehand, let us address the subject of privacy – concerns that may arise related to the reversibility of the data. Despite it being a rather hypothetical concern, it should still not be neglected. In order to lower/mitigate the risk of the data leakage, a few methods could be employed. One method is to preprocess data very well – namely removing the outliers and other uniquely identifiable features (such as Personal ID, name, age, etc.) from the set in order for the single data point not to be separately accessible (Parma Bains, 2025). Second method is generating more synthetic data than the real-world data used in the process (Parma Bains, 2025). This method prevents the data from overfitting, and make it significantly harder to re-identify. It is also a good practice to use larger datasets in general. This helps not only with the privacy but with the statistical significance as well. After that it is absolutely necessary to add random noise³ to the synthetic data.

Let us consider a thought experiment: assume all of the steps above have been completed, what would it take for someone to resurrect the original data from the synthetic data? One would need to know at least the random seed/noise and the original data structure (the volume of data), and even then, it is rather improbable that someone could reverse the data. Let us consider an example where the random noise is 5% and some feature X is equal to 100. The added noise will place the variable X in a range [95; 105], and there is no definitive outcome.

³ Adding random noise means adding some error (depicted as “ ϵ ” in econometrics). Generally, it is done in order to prevent overfitting. In this case it is to prevent reversibility.

All in all, if the process of the synthetic data generation is done with all the privacy-enhancing methods listed above taken into account, the data will be safe. However, one should not take this information for granted and should check the details at every step of the way.

Synthetic Data Generation and Evaluation Techniques

In the thesis, two methods will be employed and then compared to each other, but before that let us discuss their advantages and disadvantages, as well as the theory behind them. The two methods are Conditional Tabular Generative Adversarial Network (CTGAN) and Copula-Based Synthetic Data Generation.

CTGAN is a method specifically designed to work with tabular data. Since it is a modification of the Generative Adversarial Network (GAN), let us discuss the latter before a deep dive into CTGAN theory. GAN is a deep learning model that is composed of two neural networks – generator and discriminator (as the name implies). These two neural networks compete against each other – the generator tries to synthesize some real-world data, while the discriminator tries to tell them apart. The process is repeated until discriminator is finally unable to distinguish between the two. After this process is done, there is some random noise added to the data.

Despite functioning mainly in the same way, CTGAN still has some modifications applied to work better with both categorical and continuous variables. These modifications are Mode-Specific Normalization and the Conditional Vector Mechanism. Mode-Specific Normalization finds different modes within a variable's distribution. It then normalizes each mode separately to preserve the characteristics of the whole dataset. This greatly increases the fidelity of the data while preventing mode collapse – instead of focusing on only one mode, it helps the generator focus on multiple.

The Conditional Vector Mechanism is employed to handle categorical data. Unlike the regular GAN that handles every type of data uniformly, CTGAN adds a conditional vector into the equation – the information is fed to the noise input (typically in a one-hot encoded format). This process ensures that categorical data has its own distribution, which is closely related to its real-world counterpart. As a result, we get a balanced representation – most of the time, the variables are not uniformly distributed, and CTGAN fixes that problem. Furthermore, we get enhanced diversity and fidelity because, for the reasons mentioned above, the data becomes more accurate. The CTGAN method has its upsides such as the potential for high fidelity, the ability to capture non-linearity and the generation of realistic samples in general, however it is very high in computational cost and as a black box model, it lacks interpretability. Also, it might create the ethical biases, mitigation of which will be discussed later.

The second method, Copula, is rather statistically heavy and doesn't rely on deep learning at all. The Copula method is based on Sklar's theorem (Nelsen, 2006). It decomposes multivariate joint distributions into univariate marginal distributions. The Copula function looks at the dependence between the variables (Li, Zhao, & Fu, 2020). This method is evidently successful in finance due

to its ability to capture non-linear relationships (such as tail dependence) among the financial variables.

The process of SD generation via copula is generally split in two main stages. First and foremost, the marginal distribution is calculated from the real-world data. Depending on the goal, the method is chosen. For example, for financial risk estimation, it is generally accepted that generalized Pareto distribution is effective, because it captures extreme behavior in the data. Generally, it is said to be good practice to use the non-parametric methods in order to avoid the parametric assumptions (Zhao, 2008). However, using the non-parametric methods comes with notable limitations – while they provide a level of flexibility and avoid imposing strict distributional forms, they also struggle to capture the behavior of tail in distributions. Additionally, non-parametric methods also require large sample sizes to generalize well and provide reliable output. All in all, non-parametric methods still come out to be the best choice because they do not make strong assumptions about the distribution. Even though they may struggle with the extremities of the data, generalization is done better on normal values (non-extremities).

The second step is the selection of a copula function and parameter estimation. There are a number of copula families, but Gaussian and T-Copulas are rather popular. Based on the estimations, the copula transforms the real-world data into SD. Copula is generally an effective tool that offers very low computational costs and high interpretability. It is relatively easy to train compared to GANs. However, the problems arise when the dimensionality starts to increase – estimating marginal distributions becomes costly and exponentially complex. Also, the results are highly dependent on the copula family selection, hence it could take some time to identify the most suitable one. The choice in this case will be the Gaussian Copula, for the following reasons – it is fast, easy to estimate and fit, and most importantly, it is the only available technique in Python.

As the idea of synthetic data in finance is new, testing it with different algorithms and comparing the output could yield some valuable insights. As mentioned this thesis plans to do exactly as described above. The methods and metrics of output comparison will be discussed in the next chapter in detail.

Since the objective is to compare the metrics of different models, there is a need to create a model. The method will be Extreme Gradient Boost (XGBoost) for all models. There are many reasons to justify this choice. First, it is a highly efficient and powerful ensemble algorithm that uses the decision trees. Unlike other tree methods, this one learns and updates on its past mistakes. The benefits are increased speed, accuracy, and the ability to handle vast amounts of data. It can also handle the missing data and it deals with overfitting and correlation by itself (to a certain extent, train test split is still necessary).

XGBoost has its downsides as well – it requires fine-tuning. This process is computationally expensive and time-consuming. The choice of techniques used for parameter estimation was

narrowed down to two – Grid Search Cross Validation (GridSearchCV) and Randomized Search Cross Validation (RandomizedSearchCV).

Additionally, while GridSearchCV tries every combination from a fixed set of parameter values, RandomizedSearchCV picks a random selection of values from specified ranges. This makes it faster and still effective, especially when there's limited time or computing power. Briefly put, both techniques test different train-test splits of the data and find the optimal parameters. Since GridSearchCV had almost the same accuracy as RandomizedSearchCV, the latter was chosen, as it was less time-consuming.

The metrics chosen for the comparison of the models include accuracy, F1 score and ROC AUC Score. Accuracy is the proportion of correct predictions of the model divided by all predictions. The F1 score is a harmonic mean calculated using the formula below.

$$F_1 = \frac{2 * Precision * Recall}{Precision + Recall}$$

Precision is how many predicted positives were actually correct. Recall indicates how many actual positives were correctly predicted. One might use the F1 score because it balances precision and recall, making it a better measure than accuracy when classes are imbalanced or when both false positives and false negatives matter. The last metric that will be used for the model evaluation is the ROC AUC score. It measures how well a model distinguishes between classes. It is also useful when the classes are imbalanced because it ranks quality, not just accuracy – the ROC AUC score ranks positive instances higher than the negative ones.

Since this is a multi-class classification task, performance metrics such as precision, recall, F1 score and ROC AUC can be average across all classes using different strategies. This thesis utilizes the macro-averaging method. It calculates each metric independently for every class by treating that class as “positive” and every other class as “negative”. This is the OvR (one-vs-rest) strategy. The scores are taken and averaged in an unweighted manner, see the formula below.

$$Macro - Average = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N Metric_i$$

This approach helps make sure that all classes contribute equally to the final metric, disregarding the class size.

As mentioned, fidelity plays huge role in assessing the quality of synthetic data, particularly in understanding how well it resembles the real-world distributions. In order to quantify the fidelity, and the method called **Wasserstein distance** (also known as Earth Mover's Distance) was employed. It measures how much one distribution should be reshaped in order to look like another distance. It works by comparing the cumulative distribution functions (CDFs) of given two datasets. This is the formula:

$$W(P, Q) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |F_P(x) - F_Q(x)| dx$$

Where $F_P(x)$ and $F_Q(x)$ are CDFs of distribution P and Q respectively. This metric is suited for the continuous data, hence in order to address the categorical and boolean features the **Total Variation Distance** method was applied which measures the maximum difference in probability mass between the real and synthetic distributions. The formula for Total Variation Distance is:

$$TV(P, Q) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{x \in X} |P(x) - Q(x)|$$

Where X is the set of all possible outcomes for each feature and $P(x)$ and $Q(x)$ are the probabilities of outcome x under each distribution. Using both – Wasserstein and Total Variation Distances - ensures that fidelity is assessed accurately across all feature types. While the Wasserstein distance is readily available in Python via the package called “Scipy”, Total Variation distance is not implemented as a built-in function. Solution was to implement the mathematical equation. This approach, while manual, was straightforward and not problematic in any sense of meaning.

However this alone was not enough to get the desired information – the distances had to be normalized. This was necessary to make the Wasserstein distances comparable across features with different scales to ensure that variables with larger numeric ranges did not disproportionately influence the fidelity. To normalize the values, distances should be divided the difference between the maximum and the minimum values of x:

$$NWD(X_{real}, X_{synth}) = \frac{W_1(X_{real}, X_{synth})}{\max(X_{real}) - \min(X_{real})}$$

This process was also implemented in python and despite not being prepackaged by other developers was still not challenging to do.

Data Description & Source

Since the main focus of this thesis is not the origin of the data⁴, the decision was made to use the data from Kaggle, to be more precise “*loan_data_2007_2014*”⁵. It consisted of roughly 400,000 rows and 75 features, including personal and loan ID (identification), loan amount, personal

⁴ Except two conditions – sector should be financial and data type – tabular.

⁵ <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/devanshi23/loan-data-2007-2014>

information and other related variables. Data is authentic and, as the name suggests, it is collected from 2007 till 2014. Both personal and loan IDs were unique so there was no need for any reduction in that regard. Most of the columns were complete but there were some with little or no significance. These types of features were addressed in the preprocessing and will be discussed in detail later on. It should be mentioned that the data is originally taken from the LendingClub⁶ website and later uploaded on Kaggle.

Data Preprocessing

The preprocessing was the longest and the most labor-intensive part, as expected. Furthermore it is widely regarded to be the most important part of building the model. It is of utmost significance to understand how each feature might affect the output or each other. The process was done in Python, using simple libraries such as Pandas and Numpy.

First step was to drop all the columns that were either filled with Not a Number (NaN), Not Applicable (NA) or None. Same was done to the columns that were not completely but mostly (over 99%) filled in the same manner. However, there were certain features that made sense, despite being empty on most occasions, such as collateral amount, years in delinquency or other features related to these two.

Next step was to get rid of the personal information. Luckily there was not a lot of information that was private. Nevertheless, features like personal ID and loan ID were removed. Furthermore, as it is previously mentioned in the thesis, zip codes or address codes can both be a reason for bias in the model. In order to avoid that, both features were dropped.

Lastly, the categorical data was encoded using the Python library Label Encoder. It maps the variables to the respective numerical values. Since all of the features had only two values in the case of this dataset, the mapped values were binary (0 and 1). It is generally not a good practice to choose the label encoder in case of more than 2 variables, because it might make model “think” there is some proportional relationship between the features that might create bias or drop the accuracy. It happens because the X feature gets multiplied on 1, 2, 3... hence, creating a linear dependence.

For the categorical variable Grade, which had more than 2 possible values, the mapping was done manually and the process looked like this – A was mapped to 0, B to 1 and same for the rest. Since these coefficients are not multiplied on anything, it does not create any unnecessary linear relations, hence no statistical inaccuracies can be found.

In the process of cleaning the data, it is absolutely necessary to consider the ethical concerns as well. As mentioned above, SD tends to have a “social” bias, meaning it could discriminate a single group based on sex, skin color or other relevant factor – for example, consider a person that has certain features. Ceteris Paribus, if only variable changed is gender, it might give a different output (e.g. higher interest rate for women). This is not socially acceptable. Removing those

⁶ <https://www.lendingclub.com/>

sensitive features is not enough – “For instance, body height might act as a gender proxy, while ZIP codes could indicate race” (Pokotylo, 2024). Fortunately, this bias is easily avoidable if the data is preprocessed properly and that was done for this model.

The 400,000 data points were later reduced to 50,000. The reason was to ensure time efficiency and computational effectiveness. There is enough statistical information preserved in 50,000 data points to make synthetic data. The choice was random using shuffle method in python.

Results and Findings

In these chapters, as promised, the three types of models will be compared – one based on real-world data, one on copula and lastly CTGAN. For all three, data was split into two parts – train and test. The portions were as the accepted standard dictates – 80% train and 20% test. The normalization process was unnecessary because of the chosen method. Furthermore, it should be taken into account that for all methods RandomizedSearchCV was used in the following manner – 5 iterations with 3 cross validations. This amounted to 15 folds in total, helping save time and computational power. Let us begin with the first of the three.

Model using real-world data

The mentioned method used in the making of model was the Extreme Gradient Boost (XGBoost) algorithm. The model performed surprisingly well – the test accuracy was 78.34%. At first glance this might not seem like a lot, however it should be taken into consideration that the risk grade modeling is one of the most challenging tasks in data science, and generally, accuracy above 70% is considered good. This can be visualized on the confusion matrix on the Figure 2.I. A Confusion matrix (CM) is a very common tool for performance evaluation. Vertical axis shows the actual values and the horizontal one shows the predicted values. The correct predictions made by model align on the downward sloping diagonal.

Typically, CM is commonly seen in 2 by 2 format (for binary models with outputs 0 and 1) but it can be $n \times n$. In this case it's a 6 by 6 matrix. This is the only plausible format that one could use for such model because there are 6 possible outputs. As seen on the Figure 2.II, most important features were term (length of loan), funded amount and public record. Importance in this case refers to ability of a certain feature to “explain” the dependent variable, risk grade in this instance. The three mentioned features explain the biggest portion and hence, contribute the most in predicting the output. However, it should be mentioned that for the main objective of the thesis it is not crucial to have a high accuracy model but rather to capture the difference between real world and synthetic data models. Other interesting metrics include the Receiver-operating characteristic curve (ROC) and area under the curve (AUC) Score (Macro Average)⁷ which was 96%. ROC AUC was computed using the One-vs-Rest (OvR) strategy with macro-

⁷ Since there are more than two classes to predict, in order to show all of the information using one number, macro average had to be used.

averaging across all classes to evaluate multiclass performance, basically this score is based on the confusion matrix (Figure 2) and depicts how good the classifier is – 1.0 means it is a perfect classifier, while 0.5 is equivalent to random guessing. Less than 0.5 is a rather bad score that should not even be considered. Based on this information 96% is satisfactory. F1 Score (Macro Average) was around 67%. It is a harmonic mean of precision and recall. This score can be described as moderate. Statistics can be visualized on the graphs below, refer to Figure 2.

Figure 2. Statistics of the model based on the real-world data

Model Using Copula

To build the model, the real-world data was transformed to synthetic using the Copula method for the first case. As mentioned there are many ways to use mentioned method, the choice for

this thesis was the Gaussian Copula. This process was done using a Python package called Synthetic Data Vault (SDV). For both copula and CTGAN, the data had to be transformed into metadata. This is not a standard statistical process, but rather a technical step to ensure the data would “fit” in the prewritten program. As mentioned before synthesized data was the same size as the original one – 50000 entries. It was done surprisingly quickly – only in 5 to 6 minutes.

After that, the XGBoost was used to make a classifier, the approach was identical to that used with the real-world data. Unfortunately, the statistics were not nearly as good as in the real-world data. The accuracy was 25.5%. F1 macro average score was approximately 12 percent and the ROC AUC macro-average was 51%. All the metrics were calculated using the real-world data as the test set. It is a good practice because it shows how the model that’s trained on the synthetic data works in real world. The split in this case was not 80/20, but rather 100% synthetic for training, 20% for test from the real-world data.

As expected, copula made the data distributions smoother (refer to Figure 3). Even though the overall trends were captured correctly, the individual data points themselves did not resemble the real world case in an accurate manner. Figure 3 presents multiple features compared to their synthetic counterparts. As one can observe, the synthetic data generated with Copula works well on smoothly distributed data, but it fails on rather chaotic ones. In reality, the latter type is more common.

Let us take a look at the confusion matrix (refer to Figure 4.I). The model did a good job predicting first three classes (grades – A, B and C). However, the performance was significantly worse for the remaining classes. One plausible explanation is the class imbalance, but more on that later. In the Figure 4.II, one can observe the most significant features. It is obvious that they have changed compared to the real world model. Top 3 are revolving utilization, term and annual income. Figure 4.III displays the predicted vs real outcomes. Both, the metrics and graphs point to one conclusion – for now, it is not going to be a wise decision to use the synthetic data using copula in financial service (or at least in risk grading). The reason for this will be explained in details later on.

Fidelity was measured using the Wasserstein and Total Variance Distance methods, as mentioned before. Top features with largest distances (lowest matching with the real world counterparts) included annual income and out principle exhibit highest fidelity distance, making them the most mismatched variables. These findings and the pattern of fidelity across features align with the model performance issues discussed earlier, as poor fidelity in important variables likely contributed to the model’s weak generalization to real-world data. Average distance for all features was about 647. But as mentioned previously, unnormalized values do not bring much significance. As shown on figure 5, after normalization of distances, outstanding principle became the feature with the lowest fidelity. Average normalized fidelity was 0.0942.

Figure 3. Distributions of real world and synthetic data, Copula

Figure 4. Statistics of the model based on the Copula data

Figure 5. Fidelity Distances - Copula

Model Using CTGAN

First, let us start by mentioning that in the case of CTGAN it took significantly more time compared to the copula method – as mentioned, the latter took about 15 minutes, while former required approximately two hours. The times might vary greatly based on one’s computational power.

Two types of models were synthesized – first one, just like previously, used all 100% of the synthetic data as the training set and random 20% sample of the real-world data as the test set. The second one on the other hand used a merged version of both datasets – 50% synthetic and 50% real-world data. This combined data was later shuffled and split into two pieces – 80% train and 20% test. It is safe to say that both types of data (real and synthetic) were in equal proportion in both training and test sets.

The motivation here was experimentation. As mentioned previously, in the FCA (Financial Conduct Authority (FCA), 2024) study, the authors compared models with different proportions of the data to the benchmark model. The main idea here was the same. There was no attempt to replicate this process in case of copula, because it showed little potential for positive results compared to the CTGAN. Indeed, different proportions gave different result, but more on that later.

Same variables were chosen for the distribution comparison (refer to Figure 6). It is doubtless that there is a huge improvement. However there was a minor issue – while copula tried to smooth out the extreme values in the data, CTGAN created them artificially. This is a huge problem when it comes to preserving the statistical powers. Generally, the goal is to get rid of outliers, not create them. As seen on the Figure 6, this created unnecessary kinks in the trend, negatively affecting overall results of the model.

Unfortunately, this was not the only case when the CTGAN treated abnormalities in unusual manner. The “term” feature was exaggerated unnaturally in both models. It gave the said feature disproportionately large weight, while other possibly significant variables were underweighted. On top of that it is highly likely that CTGAN created the bias as well.

Like in the previous case the fidelity is assessed here as well using the same methodology. Annual income still remains the most mismatched feature, however there is a visible decrease in the fidelity distances of other variables. The distances are below 1000 in all but 2 cases – annual income and revol_bal. Average distance using the CTGAN was 506.5620.

Like the previous case, the values had to be normalized to make the numbers even more insightful. As seen on figure 7, the variable with least fidelity was purpose (of loan) and the variable with one of the highest fidelity was revol_bal – previously being the second worst. This once again proves the significance of normalization. Average normalized distance was 0.0508, once again proving CTGAN’s supremacy.

Figure 6. Distributions of real world and synthetic data, CTGAN

Figure 7. Fidelity Distances - CTGAN

100% synthetic, 20% real-world data in training

Let us move onto the second experiment – synthetic data model via CTGAN. As mentioned previously, this model uses 100% of the synthetic data for training and randomly selected 20% of real-world data for testing purposes.

The model was done using the XGBoost again. It visibly outperformed the copula method in all metrics. Despite this, the model was far from perfect – it had accuracy of 33.8%, which is lower than the expected accuracy of a random classifier. The F1 macro average was 24.43%, and ROC AUC macro average score was on relatively better – it was 72.44%.

As shown on the confusion matrix (refer to Figure 8.I) the model performed poorly with the classes that were not as represented. Higher risk grades like E, F... were not in the same quantities as A and B for example. It was expected from the dataset, because that is the distribution in real life as well. Imbalance among classes likely played a big role in the final results of the model, as it can be seen on the Figure 6.I. On the bright side, compared to the confusion matrix for copula (refer to Figure 4.I), this one has the upper hand – it captures the class structures better, hence improving the predictability.

50% synthetic, 50% real-world data

Final experiment was done using a hybrid model – as mentioned previously, it used 50% of synthetic and 50% of real data. 80% was randomly chosen for training and 20% was left for testing.

All the processes were conducted in the same manner – RandomizedSearchCV for hyper parameter tuning, XGBoost as a model. Metrics had a visible improvement – the accuracy increased to 52.42%, slightly better than a random guessing model this time. F1 macro average also improved – 43.98%, almost doubled compared to the previous one. The ROC AUC macro score remained the highest again with a slight improvement this time – it increased to 85.32%.

Interpretations of this model were closer to the real-world benchmarks. Confusion matrix (refer to Figure 9.I) looks somewhat similar to the real world one. The significance of the features had certain changes compared to the previous one but the “term” remained exaggerated. The “Prediction vs Actual distribution” graph (refer to Figure 9.III) has also improved a lot, however the pattern remains the same – the model continued to over predict the first and second classes and under predict the rest. Despite having relatively better metrics and higher predictability, the model still failed. Financial sector seeks for precision, and these results are not satisfactory.

Figure 8. Statistics of the model based on the CTGAN data – 100/20

Figure 9. Statistics of the model based on the CTGAN data – 50/50

Conclusion

The purpose of this thesis was to evaluate the applicability of synthetic tabular data in economic modeling by comparing two generation techniques—CTGAN and Copula—using XGBoost classifiers as the benchmark model. While the idea of synthetic data in the financial services seem very convenient the findings of this paper were a more sobering reality – the metrics consistently failed to deliver any significant results as illustrated in the summary of metrics for all models of this thesis (refer to Figure 10).

The Copula-based method performed the worst across all scenarios. Accuracy, F1 score and ROC AUC values all indicating that the model cannot be used for the real world and is worse than random guessing. The best case scenario was the hybrid model – 50/50 setup. However, even then despite having noticeable improvements in the metrics it did not perform well. Accuracy was 52%, which is a 25% deviation from the benchmark.

One of the main issues causing the underperformance of all synthetic models was the imbalance in the target variable (“credit grade”). The distribution itself was uneven – there were more people with risk grades “B” and “C” compared to individuals that had “E” or even “F”. Now this is not an issue of the data, because it is expected for the distribution to look like that in real life as well. Synthetic data generation methods disregarded the classes that were in smaller amounts (e.g. “E”, “F”) and concentrated on more represented ones. This caused a slight bias in the model that really worsened the predictability.

Despite the structured, methodical approach, this thesis faces several limitations. Most notably, the imbalance of the target variable significantly weakened the performance of the synthetic models. The rationale here was to have the data **as raw as possible** – the synthetic data should work even under the most stressful conditions. Both – Copula and CTGAN – struggled to replicate the distributions of relatively distorted variables. For example, using the Synthetic Minority Oversampling Technique (SMOTE) would mean that the data is double synthesized, which is outside the rationale of this study. Fidelity issues are seen in the key features as well. It should be mentioned that CTGAN performed relatively well, however the computational demands increase disproportionately with the increase in the volume of data. Future research should address these shortcomings by experimenting or coming up with the different approaches for synthetic data generation.

All in all, although the idea of synthetic data seems promising - offering privacy, accessibility, and flexibility - the practical results in this study were rather disappointing. The synthetic datasets failed to mimic class distributions adequately. It introduced certain distortions in feature importance, exaggerating some already prominent features and diminishing others. Synthetic models were consistently outperformed by the ones trained on the real-world data.

It should be mentioned that on the balanced data the synthetic approach might work well. It might perform better on various types of data, hence it is still a good idea to experiment with it.

However, in the case of the thesis, until the gaps that were listed before are addressed and handled properly, the synthetic data cannot add any value to the financial sector.

Figure 10. Final comparison of all metrics

Model	Accuracy	F1 Macro	ROC AUC
Real Data (Baseline)	0.7834	0.67	0.96
Copula (100% synth)	0.255	0.12	0.51
CTGAN (100% synth)	0.3381	0.2443	0.7244
CTGAN (50/50 hybrid)	0.5242	0.4398	0.8532

Bibliography

Bernoulli, J. (1713). *Ars Conjectandi*.

Financial Conduct Authority (FCA). (2024). *Using Synthetic Data in Financial Services*.

Fleming, J. M. (1962). *Domestic financial policies under fixed and floating exchange rates*. *IMF Staff Papers*, 9(3), 369–379.

Lei Xu, M. S.-I. (2019). *Modeling Tabular Data using Conditional GAN*.

Li, Z., Zhao, Y., & Fu, J. (2020). *SynC: A Copula based Framework for Generating Synthetic Data from Aggregated Sources*.

Nelsen, R. (2006). *An introduction to copulas (2nd ed.)*. Springer.

Parma Bains, T. G. (2025). *Privacy Technologies & The Digital Economy*.

Pokotylo, P. (2024). *Ethical and Legal Considerations of Synthetic Data Usage*.

Rubin, D. B. (1993). *Statistical disclosure limitation*. *Journal of Official Statistics*, 9(2), 461–468.

Sanket Kamthe, S. A. (2021). *Copula Flows for Synthetic Data Generation*.

Zhao, Z. (2008). *Parametric and nonparametric models and methods in financial econometrics*.